

STUDY OF MICROBIAL PROFILE AND THEIR ANTIBIOTIC SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN IN POSTOPERATIVE WOUND INFECTIONS FOLLOWING EMERGENCY ABDOMINAL SURGERIES: A HOSPITAL-BASED STUDY “FROM SUB-HIMALAYAN AREA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Nosocomial infections, or healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), are infections acquired during a hospital stay and not present at admission. Common types include Central Line-Associated Bloodstream Infections (CLABSI), Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTI), Surgical Site Infections (SSI), and Ventilator- Associated Pneumonia (VAP). SSIs are among the most frequent HAIs globally, with prevalence rates of 14–16%. In India, SSIs following elective surgeries range from 3.83% to 39%, and 12.41% to 26.4% in emergency surgeries. These infections are linked to prolonged hospital stays, higher treatment costs, and increased morbidity and mortality. SSIs are classified as superficial, deep, or organ/space infections, and the risk increases with the level of wound contamination—from clean to dirty surgeries. Contributing factors include microbial contamination, host immunity, emergency procedures, and comorbidities like diabetes or anaemia. This study aimed to investigate the microbial profile and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of postoperative wound infections after emergency abdominal surgeries at DRPGMC, Kangra, and to explore associated risk factors and preventive strategies.

Material and Methods:

A retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology in collaboration with the Department of Surgery at Dr. RPGMC, Kangra, from April 2023 to March 2024. The study included 113 patients who developed SSIs within 7 days post emergency abdominal surgeries. Wound swabs were collected using aseptic techniques and processed for microbial identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing using standard microbiological methods.

Results and Discussion: Out of 751 patients undergoing emergency surgeries, 113 (15.04%) developed SSIs, with a higher incidence in males (58.4%) and patients over 60 years (33.3%). Diabetes mellitus (50.4%) and anaemia (47%) were the most common comorbidities. Clean-contaminated wounds were most frequent (48.7%). Most infections were superficial (60.2%) and monomicrobial (86.6%). Gram-negative bacilli were predominant (63.2%), especially *Escherichia coli* (33.9%) and *Klebsiella pneumonia* (9.4%). Among Gram-positive cocci, *Staphylococcus aureus* was common, with 34.5% of isolates being methicillin-resistant (MRSA). Colistin and imipenem showed 100% and 89% efficacy respectively against Gram-

negative isolates, while vancomycin was universally effective against Gram-positive organisms. High resistance to ceftriaxone and piperacillin-tazobactam suggests the presence of ESBL producers.

Conclusion: This study underscores the burden of SSIs following emergency abdominal surgeries and highlights the dominance of multidrug-resistant organisms, particularly MRSA and ESBL-producing *E. coli*. Effective infection control practices, antimicrobial stewardship, and targeted therapy are essential to combat the rising incidence of resistant pathogens in postoperative wound infections.

Keywords: Surgical Site Infections (SSI) Emergency Abdominal Surgery, Postoperative Wound Infections, Nosocomial Infections, Antimicrobial Susceptibility, Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), Comorbidities, Antimicrobial Stewardship

INTRODUCTION

Nosocomial infections, also known as healthcare-associated infections (HAI), are infections that are not evident at the time of a patient's admission but are acquired during the hospital stay.¹ Common types include Central Line-Associated Bloodstream Infections (CLABSI), Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infections (CAUTI), Surgical Site Infections (SSI), and Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia (VAP).² These infections remain widespread globally. In the United States, hospital-acquired infections affect 3.2% of all hospitalized patients, 6.5% in the European Union/European Economic Area and worldwide prevalence is likely much higher. In India, the prevalence of HAI is reported to be 6.01%.³ A study conducted by V. Nair et.al showed the prevalence of HAI to be 3.76%.⁴ Postoperative wound infections persist despite modern advancements, contributing significantly to extended hospital stays, increased economic burden, and mortality.⁶ Historical contributors like Ignaz Semmelweis, Joseph Lister, and Halsted revolutionized infection control measures, emphasizing antisepsis, which remains paramount in reducing postoperative infection prevalence worldwide. Postoperative wound infections remain prevalent globally, despite modern prevention measures.⁶ These infections are associated with an increased duration of hospital stay, economic burden, and heightened morbidity and mortality.⁷ Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) are the third most commonly stated nosocomial infections, with a prevalence rate of 14–16%.⁸ In India, the prevalence of wound infections in elective surgeries ranged from 3.83% to 39%, while in emergency surgeries the prevalence ranged from 12.41% to 26.4%.⁹ Postoperative wound infection is defined as an “infection that occurs at or near a surgical incision site within 30 days of the procedure or within 90 days if an implant is left in place.”¹⁰ Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) are categorized into three primary types: Superficial wound infections are confined to the skin and soft tissues at the wound site. Deep wound infections affect deeper tissues such as muscle and fascia. Organ/space wound infections involve infections of organs or spaces other than the incised skin, fascia and muscle layer.¹¹ Wounds can be classified into four main categories based on their level of contamination. Clean Wounds are non-contaminated, uninfected surgical wounds where no inflammation is encountered. Clean-contaminated wounds involve procedures where the respiratory, gastrointestinal, or genitourinary tracts are entered under controlled conditions without significant contamination. Contaminated Wounds result from operations involving major breaks in sterile technique, spillage from the gastrointestinal tract, or traumatic wounds. Dirty wounds include traumatic injuries with delayed treatment, wounds with existing clinical infection, or those with perforated viscera.¹² The variability in infection rates is influenced by the type of surgical procedure performed, with the risk surge from surgeries classified as ‘clean’ to those regard as ‘dirty’. Specifically, the rate of infections per one thousand operations is as follows:¹³ Clean surgeries, 2.1 % infection rate, Clean- contaminated surgeries: 3.1% infections- Contaminated surgeries: 6.4% infections, Dirty surgeries: 7.1 %

infections rate.¹³ Wound infections occur when microbes contaminate a surgical site, originating from either the patient's own body (endogenous flora) or external sources (exogenous flora).¹⁴ The risk of infection is influenced by factors like the type of microorganisms, the patient's immune status, and the nature of the surgery. Emergency surgeries, underlying health conditions (e.g., diabetes, smoking), and poor surgical hygiene increase infection risk.⁶

This study aimed to identify bacterial and yeast isolates and their antimicrobial susceptibility in postoperative wound infections after emergency surgeries at DRPGMC, Kangra. It focused on infection rates, isolate patterns, and drug susceptibility, as no prior research had been conducted at this institution. Preventive strategies include prophylactic antibiotics, sterile surgical environments, proper wound care, and decolonization protocols. Intraoperative measures like minimizing tissue trauma, controlling bleeding, and using antimicrobial sutures help reduce infection risks. Postoperatively, proper wound care, early infection detection, and timely antibiotic administration are crucial for managing and preventing SSIs.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A retrospective analysis of incidence and risk factors among patients undergoing emergency abdominal surgery was performed at the Department of Microbiology at Dr.RPGMC Kangra at Tanda over a period of 1 year i.e. from April, 2023 to March, 2024. The study population included all cases having postoperative wound infections within 7 days of operation, who have undergone emergency abdominal surgeries in Department of Surgery (DRPGMC) who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. A Proforma was prepared for demographic and clinical details from all those who give consent for participation.

Clinical data: The clinical data of all patients included in the study was collected and recorded.

Collection of specimens

Swabs from surgical site were collected taking all aseptic measures as follows:
Surgical site area was wiped with sterile normal saline (0.9%).

Two sterile cotton tipped swabs moistened with sterile saline were collected by gently rolling over the surface of wound approximately 5 times, focusing on the area where evidence of pus or inflamed tissue was present.¹⁷

Sample was collected when patient develop signs of infection or inflammation.
Samples were collected and processed as per standard protocols.

RESULTS

Out of 751 patients who underwent emergency surgeries 113 developed surgical site infections. So, the incidence was found to be 15.04%. The incidence of SSI among male was 58.4%, whereas the incidence among females was 41.6% (Figure:1). Patients more than 60 years of age showed highest incidence of surgical site infections (33.3%) compared to patients in other age groups. (Figure: 2). In our study, out of 113 patients who developed post operative surgical site infections 37(32.7%) patients showed no co-morbidities. More than one risk factors co-exist in most of the patients. Patients who had anaemia were 53 accounts for 47%, Diabetes mellitus was most common co-morbidity accounts for (50.4%). Hence, the risk factors among patients developing post-operative surgical site infections were considerably higher in this study. (Table 3, Figure 3).

Figure:1

Figure:2

Sr.no	Comorbidity	Percentage%
1	Nil	32.7%
2.	Anaemia	47%
3	Diabetes Mellitus	55.4%
4	Smoker	28%
5	Hypertension	10.6%
6	COPD	1.8%
7	Other	0.9%

Table 3: Risk factor distribution

figure:3

All the surgeries were open (100%). The most common wound class identified was Clean contaminated (48.7%), followed by contaminated (38.9%) and Dirty (12.4%) wounds. (Figure 4). Majority of patients had an operation duration of 1-2 hours, accounting for 51 cases (45.5%) . Thirty patients (26.8%) had an operation duration of less than one hour (Figure 5). In our study, post-operatively drains were used in 47 patients (41.5%). In contrast,

no drains were used in 66 patients (59.5%). (figure,6) . Superficial wound infection were seen in 68(60.2%) patients and 3(2.6%) patients had organ space wound infection (figure,7).

Figure 4: Classification of wounds

Figure 5: Duration of operation

Figure 6: Distribution on basis of drain used

Figure 7: Classification of postoperative wound infections

In our study, many patients presented with overlapping signs and symptoms. The findings among the 113 patients showed that 75 (65.8%) patients had purulent discharge. This was followed by fever in 53 patients (46.5%), serous discharge in 35 patients (30.7%), and pain

and wound dehiscence in 25 (21.9%) and 24 patients (21.1%) respectively. One patient showed only redness at incision site. (figure:8).

Figure 8: Distribution of patients on basis of signs of postoperative

Wound infections

No microorganisms could be visualized directly in the smears in 28(24.7%) cases. Gram negative bacilli were seen in 67(59.29%) cases, Gram positive cocci were visualized in 36(31.7%) samples (figure,9). Samples received for culture examination showed that 20.3% samples were sterile and 79.7% showed growth of pathogenic organisms as shown in (figure:10). Monomicrobial growth in 78(86.6%) cases and polymicrobial growth in 12(13.3%) cases were seen. (figure, 11). In our study, culture revealed Gram negative bacilli in 67(63.2%) samples, Gram positive cocci in 36(34%) and fungal isolates in 3(2.8%) samples. Most common gram negative organism was *Escherichia coli* in 36(33.9%) samples, followed by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 10(9.4%) and *Acinetobacter baumannii* in 6(5.6%) samples. Among gram positive organisms most common isolate was *Staphylococcus aureus* which was further categorised into Methicillin sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* in 19(17.9%) and Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in 10(9.4%) cases. (figure: 12). The antimicrobial susceptibility pattern among Gram-negative isolates revealed that the most common drugs with 100% susceptibility was colistin, followed by imipenem (89%) and ciprofloxacin (76%). The least susceptible drug was piperacillin-tazobactam with only 26% susceptibility. For Gram-positive isolates, vancomycin exhibited the highest susceptibility at 100%, followed by cotrimoxazole (72.4%), ceftiofloxacin (65.5%), erythromycin (55.1%), and clindamycin (55.1%). The least effective drug for Gram-positive isolates was penicillin, showing only 10.3% susceptibility. Methicillin resistance was found in 34.5% of the isolates. In Enterococcus species, vancomycin remained the most effective antibiotic, with 100% susceptibility, followed by penicillin at 80%. (figure,13,14).

Figure: 9 Direct gram stain findings.

Figure 10: Distribution of samples on basis of sterile and pathogenic growth

Figure 11: Distribution of monomicrobial and polymicrobial growth

Figure: 12 Distribution on basis of Isolates.

Figure: 13 AST Pattern of Gram negative isolates

Figure: 14 AST pattern of *Staphylococcus aureus*

DISCUSSION

Postoperative wound infections, or surgical site infections (SSIs), are a significant concern after emergency abdominal surgeries. Factors such as patient comorbidities further increase the risk. Preventive measures and early detection are essential to reduce morbidity and mortality. This study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology in collaboration with the Department of Surgery at Dr. RPGMC Kangra at Tanda from April 2023 to March 2024. The incidence of SSIs was found to be 15.4%, which aligns with the 17.7% reported by Kumar A et al.¹⁸ A higher infection rate was observed in males (58.4%) compared to females (41.6%), with a male-to-female ratio of 1.4:1. Studies by Mohan N et al. and Omar A et al^{19,20} also reported a higher incidence in males, possibly due to the pro-inflammatory effects of androgens and greater involvement in high-risk activities. Comorbidities were present in 32.7% of cases, with anaemia (57%) and diabetes mellitus (55.4%) being the most common. Preoperative anaemia has been associated with postoperative complications, as shown in studies by White MC et al²¹. The prevalence of diabetes in India, as noted by Maiti S et al., is notably high at 16.1%²², further contributing to SSI risk. All surgeries in this study were open procedures. Consistent with findings by Ghimire P et al. and Kulkarni N et al., open surgeries showed a higher infection rate compared to laparoscopic procedures due to larger incisions and greater tissue handling^{23,24}. SSIs were most common in clean-contaminated wounds (48.7%), followed by contaminated (38.9%) and dirty wounds (12.4%), similar to the findings of Borle F et al. and Tripathi P et al.^{25,26} The majority (45.5%) of surgeries lasted 1-2 hours, aligning with Khan A et al.²⁷ Drain placement was noted in 41.5% of cases, particularly in contaminated and dirty wounds. Similar studies by Lilani S et al. and Khan et al^{28,27}. reported drain usage in 30% and 22.4% of cases, respectively. The most common clinical sign was purulent discharge (65.8%), followed by fever (46.5%) and serous discharge (32.7%). Wound dehiscence occurred in 21.1% of cases, consistent with findings by Jatoliya H et al²⁹ Most SSIs were superficial (60.2%), followed by deep incisional (37.1%) and organ/space infections (2.6%), comparable to Saravanakumar R et al³⁰. Out of 113 samples, 79.7% showed pathogen growth, consistent with Lilani SP et al²⁷. who reported an 82.36% culture positivity rate. Monomicrobial growth was observed in 86.6% of cases, with *Escherichia coli* (33.9%) being the most common pathogen, followed by *Staphylococcus*

aureus (27.3%). Similar results were reported by Jatoliya H et al²⁹. and Gupta S et al³¹. The predominance of Gram-negative organisms, especially Enterobacterales, is expected in abdominal surgeries due to gut flora contamination. Antibiotic susceptibility revealed 100% sensitivity of *Escherichia coli* to colistin, followed by imipenem (97.2%). High resistance to ceftriaxone (13.8%) and piperacillin-tazobactam (11.1%) suggests the prevalence of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL)-producing organisms. *Staphylococcus aureus* showed 100% susceptibility to vancomycin, though ceftazidime resistance (65.5%) indicated a high prevalence of MRSA. The study highlights the urgent need for antimicrobial stewardship and strict infection control practices. Continuous monitoring of antibiotic resistance patterns is essential to guide appropriate therapy and reduce the burden of SSIs in emergency abdominal surgeries.

CONCLUSION

The study found a 15.04% incidence of surgical site infections (SSI) in patients undergoing emergency abdominal surgeries, with a higher prevalence in males (58.4%) and older adults (33.3% in those over 60 years). Diabetes mellitus was the most common comorbidity (50.4%), followed by anaemia (47%) and smoking (28%). Clean contaminated wounds were the most frequent (48.7%), with Gram-negative bacilli being the predominant pathogens, particularly *Escherichia coli* (33.9%) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (9.4%). Among Gram-positive isolates, *Staphylococcus aureus* was common, with 34.5% showing methicillin resistance. Antimicrobial susceptibility showed colistin and imipenem as the most effective against Gram-negative bacteria, with ciprofloxacin demonstrating moderate efficacy. For Gram-positive isolates, vancomycin was universally effective, followed by cotrimoxazole and ceftazidime. The significant prevalence of resistant organisms, including MRSA, underscores the need for rigorous infection control practices, early diagnosis, and targeted antibiotic therapy. The study highlights the importance of antimicrobial stewardship to manage SSIs effectively.

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